

A STUDY ON COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CONCRETE BY REPLACEMENT OF COARSE AND FINE AGGREGATE WITH STEEL SLAG AND QUARRY DUST

MARUTLA VASEEMA, NALLAJENNU SRAVANKUMARREDDY, ARAVETI PEDIRAJU
ASSISTANT PROFESSOR^{1,2,3}

vaseema2019@gmail.com, nsravan@svitac.ac.in, peddiraju2920@gmail.com

Department of Civil Engineering, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,
N.H 44, Hampapuram, Rappthadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

ABSTRACT

As time went on, people kept looking for ways to make concrete that could withstand more and more abuse, hoping to find a solution that would work. The origins of high strength concrete (HSC) may be traced back around 35 years. The development of water-reducing admixtures in the late 1960s paved the way for high strength precast products, and structural components in beams were produced in situ using HSC. Concrete grades M60 to M120 are routinely utilised when technology has matured. Under controlled laboratory circumstances, concrete with a Mohs hardness of 200 and higher is feasible. High strength concretes are defined in an evolving way. High strength concrete was defined at 34 N/mm² in the 1950s, and by the 1960s, compressive strengths of 52 N/mm² were being utilised commercially. Recent years have seen the application of cast-in-place structures with compressive strengths close to 138N/mm². The advent of pre-stressed concrete technology has provided a reason to produce highly-strengthened concrete. Bridges that are pre-stressed using concrete with a strength ranging from 35N/mm² to 45N/mm² are constructed in India using high strength concrete. One of the flyovers in Mumbai is now using concrete with a strength of 75 N/mm². The Kaiga power project's containment dome was built using High Strength Concrete (HSC) with silica fume as one of its constituents; the strength of this concrete was 60MPa. The gas, oil, nuclear, and power sectors are only a few of the many global users of high strength concrete (HSC). Greater structural performance, environmental friendliness, and energy conservation are driving the ever-increasing use of such concrete. Not only are these concretes often in danger of fire, but they are also subjected to extreme heat and pressure for long periods of time. Using 10%, 15%, 20%, and 30% fly ash as admixtures per weight of cement, with a constant amount of 0.5% steel hook fibres added per volume of concrete, this study examined the effects of various admixtures on the resistance, workability, durability, and compressive strength of concrete, as well as their combined effects.

Important Terms: High Strength Concrete, Workability, Longevity, and Compressive Strength.

INTRODUCTION

impact. The lack of virgin aggregates, such as dirt and rubble, is especially acute in the alluvial plain region.

The unparalleled quality of being formed in any desired shape makes concrete the most extensively used man-made building material worldwide. The current infrastructure demands a material that is both strong and long-lasting, and this material has quickly become the material of choice. Worldwide, annual concrete use is close to five billion metric tonnes, which accounts for 25–30% of national budgets. Due to its massive use in current building methods and the fact that per capita consumption has reached over 2 kg, it is also an unavoidable substance in human existence. It was a wise choice for India to invest in 21st-century infrastructure including fast highways, airports, ports, power plants, and tourist attractions. Concrete is essential in the modern construction industry since it is used in every part of building. Because of its many desirable qualities, including strength and longevity, concrete has been the material of choice for all new infrastructure projects. There is a significant economic impact

from the ongoing depletion of natural resources and the energy needed to process them. However, there is a way to recycle these particles and put them to use in new structural applications while reducing this impact.

A wide range of concrete additives may be used to alter the material's characteristics, making it suitable for a wide range of applications. Following India's independence, it saw extensive use in the country's infrastructure development. In order to achieve the goals of radiation attenuation and resistance to heavy machines, it is necessary to increase the mass of concrete per unit of area. This is because these properties are density dependent and are unaffected by the kind of material used. The tensile strength of concrete is negligible compared to its compressive strength, which is very significant. Because of this, it is common practice to strengthen it with materials that are robust under stress, such as steel. The freezing of stored water is one of numerous processes that may harm concrete. Another is the permeability of the concrete composition. In order to counteract concrete's harm, high-quality components must be employed in its mix. Concrete is the material of choice this century, but its constituents are running low owing to its extensive use. As a result, producing high-quality concrete is challenging owing to a lack of available resources; one possible solution is to recycle, reuse, or replace the materials used. One of the better possibilities is recycling, and research on recovered aggregates has already begun. The various components used to make concrete have strengths that are transferred to the final concrete composite. Although recycled aggregates and other secondary materials may not initially provide a large amount of aggregate, their usage in high-demand applications might significantly cut down on the amount of natural aggregate needed by the building sector. Secondary materials may not be able to solve the resultant aggregate shortage entirely, but they may help make it more manageable.

1.5.1

Goals

The primary goals of this study are: — to investigate the aggregate characteristics of ceramic debris. In order to evaluate ceramic aggregate's qualities in comparison to those of natural aggregate. Investigating the potential use of ceramic waste aggregate in concrete. To investigate how acid affects ceramic aggregate concrete while it is still fresh. - To investigate how acid affects ceramic aggregate concrete after it has hardened.

MATHEMATICAL

QUALITIES

3.1 INTRODUCTION Cement, when combined with water, bonds fine and coarse particles together to form concrete, an artificial substance. The revolutionary changes brought about by the concrete's intrinsic properties are largely responsible for the material's meteoric rise to fame and ubiquity. Part 3.2: The Used Materials' Characteristics. Standard coarse and fine aggregate, steel slag, quarry dust, and 53-grade cement were all tested for their qualities in accordance with the requirements of IS 2386:1963. Additionally, the table displays the findings.

The project calls for M25 grade concrete. The air-cooled slag utilised in this process is sourced from NELCAST PVT LIMITED in Atchudur, S.P.S.R. NelloRE district, and its properties are detailed in section 3.2.1. One byproduct of the steelmaking process is the formation of steel slag. It is a ceramic substance that is not metallic and is produced when flux, such calcium oxide, reacts with the inorganic, non-metallic elements that are already in the steel waste. —In all our building projects, we prioritise environmental responsibility. By substituting steel slag for the natural aggregates, we are able to reduce our impact on the environment and find a more long-term, sustainable solution.

—The technical features, low maintenance requirements, and high strengths of steel slag make it our material of choice for many building projects. Furthermore, steel slag aggregates provide many benefits, including improved durability, resistance to rutting, and excellent skid resistance. A longer lifespan for the building is another benefit.

Table: 1 physical properties of steel slag

Properties	Steel slag
Specific gravity	2.6
Loose density	1382kg/m ³
Compacted density	1520kg/m ³
Fineness Modulus	-
Grading Zone	-
Crushing strength	26
Impact strength	12.86

by

PROPERTIES OF QUARRY DUST.

After rocks are extracted and processed to create tiny particles smaller than 4.75 mm, the resulting residue, tailing, or other non-volatile waste material is called quarry dust. You may use this product to make asphalt, replace sand, or fill up spaces around pipes. As a more cost-effective substitute for river sand, quarry dust may be used. The high shipping costs make common river sand a luxury item.

From natural sources, also large scale depletion of the sources creates environmental problems.

We need to find a new product for the concrete industry since river sand is becoming less appealing due to environmental concerns and other restrictions. Quarry rock dust, instead of river sand, might be a more cost-effective option in this case.

PRELIMINARY TESTS ON MATERIALS

GENERAL

The characteristics of the concrete materials used in the experimental and mix design process are covered in this chapter. Cement, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, water, steel slag, and aggregates from quarries were used in the experiments. The purpose of this chapter is to determine whether the materials are appropriate for use in concrete by conducting tests on them, comparing the results to standard values, and drawing conclusions.

CEMENT

The following tests were conducted in accordance with IS: 8112 - 1989 on the ordinary Portland cement 53 grade BHARATI that conforms to IS: 12269. In the concrete technology laboratory, things like cement's specific gravity, fineness, normal consistency, and beginning and final setting times are measured. Table 3.1 displays the outcomes of the experiments, which were compared with the IS specification.

Sl.No	Tests	Experimented values	Suggested values as per IS specification
1	Fineness of cement	4%	< 10%
2	Normal consistency	30%	—
3	Specific gravity	3.05	< 3.15
4	Initial setting time	75 min	Min of 30 min
5	Final setting time	265 min	Max of 10 hrs

WORKABILITY OF CONCRETE

Workability

A concrete's workability is defined as its mixability, transportability, mouldability, and compactability, which are four of the material's partial characteristics. In its early stages, new concrete has both cohesiveness and consistency. One way to evaluate concrete's compactability and finishability is by looking at its cohesiveness.

The consistency of the concrete is determined by the amount of water needed for mixing. The workability of concrete, in broad strokes, is defined as the effort required to compress the material in a certain mould. The required workability of a mix in reinforced concrete is affected by the kind of compaction that is employed and the complexity of the reinforcing. Separation is undesirable in a practical mixture. What follows is a discussion of the workability partial characteristics.

BEHAVIOUR OF STEEL SLAG & QUARRY DUST AGGREGATE CONCRETE UNDER COMPRESSION

INTRODUCTION

After a thorough literature review, it was determined that steel slag coarse aggregate should replace coarse aggregate in concrete production. This will allow future generations to have access to natural aggregate and significantly lower the cost of producing concrete in areas where there is an abundance of steel slag aggregate. Presented in Chapter 3 are the numerous components and their attributes that have been suggested for this experiment. The experimental findings and thorough descriptions of the tests used to determine how steel slag concrete behaves under compression are presented in this chapter.

Mix proportion

Mix proportion of 0.48: 1: 1.53: 2.88 is chosen according to its ingredients i.e., water, cement, fine aggregate and coarse aggregate.

Water: Locally available borewell water was used for mixing and curing.

Cement: OPC53 grade of BHARATHI cement was used.

Fine aggregate: Locally available sand passing through 4.75mm IS sieve and retaining on 2.36 mm IS sieve was used.

Coarse aggregate: Locally available coarse aggregate and ceramic aggregate of size 12mm and 20 mm are used.

The quantity of materials used for the experimentation of work is tabulated in table 5.1.

Materials (kg)	Replacement of C.A by Ceramic aggregate					
	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
Cement	10	10	10	10	10	10
Fine aggregate	15.3	15.3	15.3	15.3	15.3	15.3
Natural crushed aggregate	28.8	23.04	17.28	11.52	5.76	0
Ceramic aggregate	0	5.76	11.52	17.28	23.04	28.8

Curing of concrete specimens

In order to regulate how quickly and how much water evaporates from concrete as the cement hydrates, the process is called curing. Due to the fact that hydrating

curing the cement for a fair amount of time is necessary for the concrete to reach its strength and durability potential; this process might take days or even weeks instead of hours. Since the pace of cement hydration is affected by temperature, controlling the temperature is also a part of curing.

Fig.5.5 Cube moulds allowed drying in moisture for 24 hours

Fig.5.6 curing of concrete specimens in water

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Workability of concrete

Workability of a concrete is a term which consists of the following four partial properties of concrete namely mixability, transportability, mould ability, and compactability. Cohesiveness and consistency both are concurrent properties of fresh concrete. Cohesiveness is a measure of the compact

concrete's capacity and its finishability. The consistency of the concrete is determined by the amount of water needed for mixing. The concrete's workability is affected by both its qualities and the specifics of its application. Although it may seem that concrete in very dry conditions has poor workability and that

it has great workability in extremely wet conditions, none of these extremes is ideal for enhancing concrete's desirable properties. Test findings, slump, and compaction factor when various ceramic substitutes are used

aggregate and acid are shown in tables 6.1, 6.2, 6.3, 6.4.

Table 6.1 Test results of slump with different replacements for 5% Hcl

Sl.No	Nomenclature	% of Hcl	Percentage replacement of natural coarse aggregate with ceramic waste aggregate	Slump value in mm
1	R	5	0	150
2	CWAC20	5	20	140
3	CWAC40	5	40	130
4	CWAC60	5	60	125
5	CWAC80	5	80	122
6	CWAC100	5	100	120

Weight Loss

Test results of weight loss of ceramic concrete with 5% acid & 10% acid are shown in Table 7.9, 7.10, 7.11, 7.12.

Table 7.9 Weight Loss of Ceramicconcretewith 5% acid for7 days

SLNo	% of Ceramic	% of Acid	Weight (gm)
1	0	5	8154
2	20	5	8013
3	40	5	7940
4	60	5	7879
5	80	5	7798
6	100	5	7705

Table 7.10 Weight Loss of Ceramic concrete with 5% acid for 28 days

SLNo	% of Ceramic	% of Acid	Weight (gm)
1	0	5	8415
2	20	5	8295
3	40	5	8212
4	60	5	8138
5	80	5	8004
6	100	5	7889

6.3Closure

The slump of conventional concrete with 5%and10%Hclwasfoundtobe150mmand 130mmrespectively.TheCompactionfactor of conventional concrete with 5% and10% Hcl was found to be 0.93 and 0.89. Theslumpvalueandcompactionfactorgraduallydecreasedwithincreaseinreplacement of coarse aggregate by ceramicaggregate both at 5% and 10% Hcl. The 28days compressive strength of conventionalconcrete with 5% and 10% Hcl was found tobe43.33and42.44MParespectively.The 28dayscompressivestrengthofconcretewithreplacementofcoarseaggregatebyceramicwasteaggrega tewith5%Hclatan intervalof20%from0to100%wasfound

tobe 42.07, 41.78, 41.33, 40.74, 35.41 MPa

respectively. The 28 days compressive strength of concrete with replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic waste aggregate with 10% Hcl at an interval of 20% from 0 to 100% was found to be

41.78, 41.33, 40.74, 40.15, 34.67 MPa

respectively. The decrease in workability and compressive strength of ceramic aggregate concrete was mainly because of its shape, surface texture, and water absorption.

CONCLUSIONS

Workability

Workability of ceramic aggregate concrete is decreased when the aggregate is replaced with ceramic waste and when the normal water is replaced with hydrochloric acid.

Slump value

The slump value has been decreased from 150 mm to 120 mm at 5% addition of Hcl. At 10% addition of Hcl, the slump has been decreased from 130 mm to 90 mm.

Compaction factor

Compaction factor has been decreased from 0.93 to 0.85 at 5% addition of Hcl. At 10% addition of Hcl the compaction factor has been decreased from 0.89 to 0.81.

7 days Compressive strength

The average 7 days compressive strength of reference mix at 5% Hcl is 36.67 Mpa.

The average 7 days compressive strength of reference mix at 10% Hcl is 31.55 Mpa.

At 5% Hcl

When normal aggregate is replaced with ceramic aggregate at 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100%, the compressive strength shows as 35.11, 32.89, 29.04, 25.78 and 23.41

Mpa. These values show that compressive strength is reduced to 32.32% at 100% replacement with ceramic waste.

At 10% Hcl

When normal aggregate is replaced with ceramic aggregate at 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100%, the compressive strength shows as 29.77, 28.14, 26.67, 24.74 and 23.11

Mpa. These values show that compressive strength is reduced to 22.37% at 100% replacement with ceramic waste.

28 days Compressive strength

The average 28 days compressive strength of reference mix at 5% Hcl is 43.33

Mpa. The average 28 days compressive strength of reference mix at 10% Hcl is 42.44 Mpa.

At5%Hcl

Whennormalaggregateisreplacedwithceramicaggregateat20%,40%,60%,80%

and 100%, the compressive strength showsas42.07,41.78,41.33,40.74and35.41Mpa.

Thesevaluesshowthatcompressivestrengthisreducedto15.83%at100%replacementwith ceramicwaste.

At10%Hcl

Whennormalaggregateisreplacedwithceramic aggregate at 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%and 100%, the compressive strength showsas41.78,41.33,40.74,40.15and34.64

Mpa. These values show that compressivestrengthisreducedto17.09%at100%replacementwith ceramicwaste.

Weightloss

At5%Hcltheweightlossofceramicaggregateconcreteat7days and 28dayswasfoundtobe0.96%and6.02%respectively. At 10% Hcl the weight loss ofceramic aggregate concrete at 7 days and 28dayswasfoundtobe4.62%and2.76%respectively.

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